

Colour atmospheres as a non-verbal approach to preferences and behavioural states in forensic psychiatry

A qualitative case study comparing representational nature images and abstract colour compositions in patients with severe communication impairments

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Abstract

Background: Patients in forensic psychiatric settings with severe cognitive and communicative impairments largely elude established diagnostic and participatory procedures. In particular, there is a lack of valid methods for systematically recording individual preferences and affective reactions without linguistic mediation.

Objective: The aim of the study is to investigate the extent to which non-verbal behavioural reactions to colour atmospheres can serve as a reliable means of accessing individual preferences.

The central question is whether abstract colour atmospheres trigger comparable affective/physical reactions to concrete images of nature, provided that their colour and lighting mood is preserved.

Method: A qualitative, idiographic case study (N = 2) was conducted under real-world conditions in a forensic psychiatric setting.

The subjects were presented with 20 archetypal images of nature as well as 20 colour-atmospheric abstractions.

Non-verbal behavioural responses (facial expressions, body movements, vocalisations, duration of attention) were recorded in two sessions (fixed vs. randomised order) by the researcher and trained nursing staff.

Results: Both patients exhibited clear, reproducible and, in some cases, strongly pronounced affective-physical reactions to the stimuli presented. The reaction patterns were highly consistent between representational nature images and the corresponding abstract colour gradients (congruence up to 90%). Open, light and warm colour atmospheres led to approach behaviour, relaxation and longer dwell times, whilst dense, dark and visually complex atmospheres correlated with avoidance and tension. These differentiated reactions were observed in patients who had previously been largely unreachable through attempts at verbal communication.

Conclusion: The results provide initial empirical evidence that colour atmospheres can constitute an independent and primary factor influencing emotional experience and behaviour, even independently of representational image content. At the same time, the approach opens up a novel way of assessing individual preferences in nonverbal patient groups.

Despite the limited sample size, the findings suggest that colour-atmospheric design can be specifically employed for emotional regulation and to support therapeutic processes.

1. Introduction

The perception of the environment is not determined exclusively by objects and forms, but significantly by atmospheric qualities such as colour, light and spatial openness, which can directly modulate emotional experience and behaviour. Within the framework of evidence-based colour psychology, according to Buether, colour atmospheres are understood as central modulators of emotional and behavioural reactions, which also take effect below the level of conscious, language-mediated processing.

In forensic psychiatry, patients with severe communication impairments remain largely excluded from diagnostic, therapeutic and design-related decision-making processes, as their subjective preferences cannot be expressed verbally.

The theoretical basis is an interdisciplinary approach drawing on somatic marker theory (Damasio), colour-in-context theory (Elliot & Maier) and evidence-based health architecture (Ulrich et al.).

Common to these approaches is the assumption that visual stimuli . particularly colour and lighting moods . can trigger immediate affective and physical reactions that influence behaviour without necessarily being reflected in language.

Against this background, the present study systematically investigates for the first time whether comparable emotional and behavioural reactions to representational nature images and their abstract colour atmospheres can be observed in patients with severe communication impairments.

This addresses the question of whether colour atmospheres can function as an independent variable that is perceived and evaluated independently of representational imagery.

2. Research questions and hypotheses

2.1. Research questions

1. Can stable colour preferences be identified through non-verbal behaviour?
2. Are reactions to representational nature images and the abstract colour atmospheres derived from them comparable?
3. Do the results suggest that colour atmospheres trigger comparable emotional and behavioural reactions regardless of the representational content of the images?
4. What insights do the observed reaction patterns provide for the therapeutically supportive design of patient rooms and other highly sensitive clinical environments?

2.2. Hypotheses

H1: Colour atmospheres trigger consistent behavioural responses.

H2: Representational images of nature and the abstract colour atmospheres derived from them elicit comparable reactions, provided that the underlying mood created by the colours and light is preserved.

H3: Differences between reactions to images and abstractions indicate context-dependent effects.

3. Methodology

3.1. Study design

Qualitative single-case study (idiographic approach) with systematic observation.

3.2. Sample

Patient A: male, 60 years old, chronic paranoid schizophrenia (ICD-10 F20.0), severe communication disorder, high sensory sensitivity.

Medication (daily dose): Clozapine 400 mg, Promethazine 200 mg, Diazepam 27 mg, Benperidol 15 mg

Patient B: male, 39 years old, early childhood autism (F84.0) and moderate intellectual disability (F71.1), pronounced communication deficits and sensory hypersensitivity.

Medication (daily dose): Levomepromazine: 200 mg, Zuclopenthixol: 40 mg

Both patients were admitted under Section 126a of the Code of Criminal Procedure and exhibited recurrent aggressive and self-harming behaviour.

3.3. Stimuli

- . 20 archetypal images of nature with a wide range of atmospheric qualities
- . 20 colour gradients derived from these (AI-generated and manually optimised)

The deliberate non-standardisation of brightness and saturation served to preserve the characteristic differences between the respective colour atmospheres and thus ensure a perception scenario as close to reality as possible. The natural images were selected with the aim of depicting as broad a spectrum as possible of archetypal environmental and colour atmospheres.

3.4. Procedure

- Presentation: A3 prints
- Duration: 15.20 seconds per stimulus
- Round 1: fixed order
- Round 2: randomised order
- Setting: Patient room under natural and artificial lighting

The second trial served to verify the stability of the observed response patterns regardless of the order of presentation.

3.5. Data collection

The following were recorded on a standardised observation form:

- Facial expressions
- Posture and movements (approach/avoidance)
- Vocalisations
- Duration

Data collection was exploratory, without a predefined coding scheme. Observers: the researcher (author) and two trained nursing staff.

A predefined coding scheme was deliberately avoided in order to allow for the most open and phenomenologically accurate recording of behavioural responses. Parallel observation by the researcher and trained nursing staff served to ensure the inter-subjective reliability of the assessments.

3.6. Ethics

Participation was based on consent from the patient.s carer in accordance with Section 1901a of the German Civil Code (BGB). Consultation took place with the treating specialists. No formal ethical approval was sought. For data protection reasons, no image, audio or video recordings were made apart from the documentation of behavioural reactions.

The study was conducted in consultation with the treating specialists and in accordance with the Institutions internal policies.

4. Results

Both patients showed:

- stable preference clusters
- high reproducibility
- positive reactions to open, warm colour atmospheres (field, coast)

The high degree of agreement between image and colour gradient reactions suggests that the **colour atmosphere represents a primary influencing factor**.

5. Individual evaluations of Patient A and Patient B

5.1. Patient A . Individual evaluation

5.1.1. General assessment of the images (Phase 1)

Patient A showed many neutral/negative reactions overall, but clearly defined positive preferences.

Positive preference reaction:

- Desert 1: long smile, cheerful impression/relaxed, prolonged viewing, very favourable.
- Coast 9.1: smile, cheerful impression, body leaning forward.
- Coast 9.3: smile, cheerful, arms open, prolonged viewing.
- Fields 11.1.11.3: repeated (sometimes long) smile, consistently positive, body relaxed/leaning forward, long to very long viewing duration.

Neutral / no preference:

- Savannah 2, Rainforest 3, Tundra 4, Taiga 5, Deciduous forest 6/6.1, Mountains 7/7.1, Steppe 8, Coast 9.1/9.2, Arctic 10, Field 11: no emotional reaction, no physical reaction.

Negative preference reaction:

- Deciduous forest 6.2: very averse, grim expression, grumbling sounds, head turned away.
- Coast 9: neutral to averse, tense gaze, listless.

Checklist: Colour atmospheres

2025

Title	Image	Tick:		Describe the patient's reactions:			
		Positive	Negative	Emotional reactions	Physical reactions	Temporal behaviour	Note
1. Desert		x		smiles for a long time and seems cheerful	relaxed	looks at the picture for a long time	very fond
2. Savannah			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
3. Rainforest			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
4. Tundra			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
5. Tago			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
6. Deciduous forest			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
6.1. Deciduous forest			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
6.2. Deciduous forest			x	very averse, grim expression, growling sounds	turns head away	-	-
7. Mountains			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
7.1. Mountains			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
8. Steppes & Plateau			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
9. Coast			x	neutral, disinterested, tense look	no reaction	-	seems listless
9.1. Coast		x		smiles	leaning forward	-	-
9.2. Coast			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
9.3. Coast		x		smiles looks cheerful	opens arms	long gaze	very positive and active attitude
10. Arctic & Antarctic			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
11B. field			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
11.1. Field		x		smiles	no reaction	long gaze	seems satisfied
11.2. Field		x		smiles	no reaction	long look	-
11.3. Field		x		very pleased smiles for a long time	Upper body leaning towards the picture	very long observation	even the patient smiles even when shown repeatedly

Fig. 1: Observation log: Colour atmospheres: Patient A . Phase 1

Checklist: Colour gradients

2025

Title	Image	Tick the box:		Describe the patient's reactions:			
		Positive	Negative	Emotional reactions	Physical reactions	Temporal behaviour	Note
1. Desert		x		smiles	relaxed	slowly, prolonged gaze	very fond of
2. Savannah			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
3. Rainforest			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
4. Tundra			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
5. Tago			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
6. Deciduous forest			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
6.1. Deciduous forest			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
6.2. Deciduous forest			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
7. Mountains			x	A very slight smile	no reaction	-	-
7.1. Mountains			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
8. Steppes & Plateau			x	No reaction	no reaction	-	-
9. Coast			x	No response	no response	-	-
9.1. Coast		x		smiles slowly	relaxed, moves his arms	long, deep contemplation	-
9.2. Coast			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
9.3. Coast		x		smiles	affectionate	long gaze	very fond
10. Arctic & Antarctic			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
11B. field			x	no reaction	no reaction	-	-
11.1. Field		x		smiles	leaning forward	long gaze	very fond
11.2. Field			x	slight smile	no reaction	long gaze	seems interested
11.3. Field		x		smiles for a long time and seems cheerful	moves towards the picture	long contemplation	very fond

Fig. 2: Observation log for colour gradients: Patient A . Phase 2

5.1.2. General assessment of colour gradients (Phase 2)

Here, too, there were many neutral/dislike reactions, but clearly defined positive preferences.

Positive preference reaction:

- Desert 1: smiling, relaxed, prolonged viewing, very favourable.
- Coast 9.1: smiling, cheerful impression, physical activity, intense and prolonged viewing.
- Mountains 7: slight smile, no physical reactions.
- Coast 9.3: smiling, body leaning forward, relaxed posture.
- Field 11.1.11.3: smiling, sometimes prolonged smiling, prolonged viewing, body relaxed, leaning forward and sometimes active.

Neutral/no preference reaction:

- Savannah 2, Rainforest 3, Tundra 4, Taiga 5, Deciduous forest 6/6.1/6.2, Mountains 7/7.1, Steppe 8, Coast 9/9.2, Arctic 10, Field 11: no emotional reactions, no physical reactions.

5.1.3. Comparison of image vs. colour gradient (congruence, Patient A)

In Patient A, both the centrally positive and the unresponsive/neutral stimuli showed high congruence between image and gradient:

Fig. 3: Colour atmospheres with a positive effect, Patient A – Phase 1

Fig. 4: Colour gradients with a positive effect, Patient A – Phase 2

A. Identical positive preference reaction:

- Desert 1, Coast 9.1, Coast 9.3, Field 11.1. and 11.3.

B. Identical neutral/no preference reaction:

- Savannah 2, Rainforest 3, Tundra 4, Taiga 5, Deciduous forest 6/6.1, Mountains 7.1, Steppe 8, Coast 9.2, Arctic 10, Field 11.

C. Divergent preference reaction:

- Deciduous forest 6.2: Phase 1 very averse (grim, head turned away) → Phase 2 no reaction
- Mountain 7: Phase 1: no reaction → Phase 2: slightly positive (slight smile)
- Coast 9: Phase 1 tense expression, averse → Phase 2 no reaction

Overall, **17 out of 20 motifs (85% congruence)** showed identical valence reactions between images and colour gradients, with slight deviations occurring in only three structurally rich motifs (deciduous forest 6.2, mountains 7, coast 9).

5.2. Patient B. . Individual evaluation

5.2.1. General assessment of the images (Phase 1)

Patient B displayed a high degree of emotional and physical expressiveness with clear approach and avoidance markers.

Checklist: Colour atmospheres

2025

Title	Image	Tick the box:		Describe the patient's reactions:			
		Positive	Negative	Emotional reactions	Physical reactions	Temporal behaviour	Note
1. Desert			X	neutral, disinterested	neutral	brief reflection	rather negative, neutral
2. Savannah		X		smiles	leaning towards	long, lingering gaze	positive expression
3. Rainforest			X	sobbing	tense	brief reflection	-
4. Tundra			X	Groaning	turns her head away	brief glance	negative
5. Tapes			X	tense	closes its eyes	brief observation	noticeably negative
6. Deciduous forest		X		extreme laughter, joyful	relaxed, open	long, deep contemplation	very affectionate
6. 1. Deciduous forest			X	hesitant, neutral, disinclined	looks away	brief glance	-
6. 2. Deciduous forest			X	sad, weeping	leans back	brief contemplation	-
7. Mountains		X		smiles	relaxed	long contemplation	-
7. 1 Mountains			X	weeps, averse	turns face away	brief contemplation	-
8. Steppe & Prairie		X		smiles	relaxed	long contemplation	-
9. Coast			X	smiling hesitantly	-	shorter than before	unstable, hesitates for a long time
9.1. Coast		X		laughs, joy	leans forward	long gaze	very fond
9.2. Coast		X		lovestruck gaze, dreamy, enthusiastic	relaxed	long gaze	very fond
9.3. Coast		X		smiles for a long time	relaxed	long gaze	-
10. Arctic & Antarctic			X	crying, averse	turns her head away	brief contemplation	-
11. Field			X	weeps, disinclined	oppressed	brief reflection	-
11.1. Field		X		smiles	relaxed, calm	long contemplation	very fond
11.2. Field		X		smiling	relaxed	long gaze	very fond
11.3. Field		X		looks pleased, eyes appear lively	Body reacts joyfully	long gaze	very affectionate

Fig. 5: Observation log: Colour atmospheres: Patient B . Phase 1

Checklist: Colour gradients

2025

Title	Image	Tick:		Describe the patient's reactions:			
		Positive	Negative	Emotional reactions	Physical reactions	Temporal behaviour	Note
1. Desert			X	hesitates, reluctant	sluggish	brief reflection	-
2. Savannah		X		is looking forward to	cheerful	long contemplation	-
3. Rainforest			X	sad	bent	brief reflection	Mood drops
4. Tundra			X	unwilling	limp	brief observation	-
5. Tapes			X	reluctant	slumped, sluggish	brief observation	-
6. Deciduous forest		X		smiles, is happy	moves towards the picture	long contemplation	inspires him
6. 1. Deciduous forest			X	reluctant	sluggish	brief consideration	-
6. 2. Deciduous forest			X	looks sad	sluggish	brief reflection	-
7. Mountains		X		smiles	leaning forward	long gaze	-
7. 1 Mountains			X	tense, sad	body leaning away	brief contemplation	stressed
8. Steppe & Prairie			X	hesitant, neutral, averse	looks away	brief glance	-
9. Coast			X	reluctant	looks away	brief reflection	-
9.1. Coast		X		smiles slowly	relaxed	long contemplation	-
9.2. Coast		X		smiles for a long time	relaxed	long contemplation	-
9.3. Coast		X		smiles, seems cheerful	Posture is straight	long observation	appears very cheerful
10. Arctic & Antarctic			X	disinterested	looks away	brief glance	-
11. Field			X	lack of interest	-	brief consideration	-
11.1. Field		X		smiles, eyes shining	bends forward	long, rapt contemplation	very fond
11.2. Field			X	hesitates, neutral	-	brief consideration	-
11.3. Field		X		laughs loudly, is very happy	leans forward	long gaze	very fond

Fig. 6: Observation log for colour gradients: Patient B . Phase 2

Positive preference reaction:

- Savannah 2: smiles, leans forward, views for a long time, enjoys the image, views for a long time.
- Deciduous forest 6: beaming smile, joy, relaxed and open posture, very receptive, looks at the image for a long time.
- Mountains 7: smiles, relaxed, long viewing duration.
- Steppe & Prairie 8: smiles, relaxed, views for a long time.
- Coast 9.1: laughter, joy, leaning forward, very affectionate, prolonged gaze.
- Coast 9.2: loving gaze, dreamy, enthusiastic, relaxed, very affectionate, long duration of observation.
- Coast 9.3: smiles for a long time, relaxed, long viewing duration.
- Field 11.1: smiles, relaxed, calm, very affectionate, long viewing time.

- Field 11.2: smiling, relaxed, very affectionate, long viewing duration.
- Field 11.3: delighted, gaze appears lively, body gestures joy (activated), very affectionate, long viewing duration.

Negative preference reaction:

- Desert 1: neutral-negative, disinterested, brief viewing.
- Rainforest 3: sobbing, tense, brief viewing
- Tundra 4: groaning, turning head away, brief viewing.
- Taiga 5: tense, eyes closed, brief viewing, conspicuously negative.
- Deciduous forest 6.1: hesitant, neutral, looks away, brief observation.
- Deciduous forest 6.2: sad, crying, leaning backwards, brief observation.
- Mountains 7.1: crying, averse, turning face away, brief viewing time.
- Coast 9: hesitant smile, slow, uncertain, shorter viewing time.
- Arctic & Antarctic 10: crying, averse, head turned away, short viewing duration.
- Field 11: crying, averse, anxious, short viewing duration.

5.2.2. General assessment of the colour gradients (Phase 2)

Positive preference reaction:

- Savannah 2: joy, cheerful, long viewing time.
- Deciduous forest 6: smiling, joy, leaning forward, active, long viewing time.
- Mountains 7: smiling, joy, leaning forward, long viewing time.
- Coast 9.1: a long smile, relaxed, long viewing time.
- Coast 9.2: smiles for a long time, relaxed, looks at the camera for a long time.
- Coast 9.3: smiling, very cheerful, upper body upright, long duration of observation.
- Field 11.1: smiling, beaming, leaning forward, very affectionate, enjoyment, long viewing duration.
- Field 11.3: delighted, gaze appears lively, body gestures joy (activated), very affectionate, long viewing duration.

Negative preference reaction:

- Desert 1: hesitant, averse, sluggish posture, short viewing duration.
- Rainforest 3: sad, slumped, short viewing duration, mood drops.
- Tundra 4: averse, limp, short viewing duration.
- Taiga 5: disinclined, slumped, sluggish, short viewing duration.
- Deciduous forest 6.1: averse, sluggish, short viewing duration.
- Deciduous forest 6.2: sad, listless, brief observation.
- Mountains 7.1: initially neutral, tense, looking away, stressed, brief viewing time.
- Steppe 8: hesitant, then neutral, aversion, gaze averted, short viewing duration.
- Coast 9: averse, gaze averted, short viewing duration.
- Arctic & Antarctic 10: averse, gaze averted, short viewing duration.
- Field 11: disinterested, brief viewing time.

Neutral/no preference reaction:

- Field 11.2: neutral, hesitant, short viewing duration

5.2.3. Comparison of image vs. colour gradient (congruence, Patient B)

Patient B shows very high congruence between atmospheric images (Phase 1) and colour gradients (Phase 2) with almost identical preference patterns

1 Colour schemes with a positive effect, Patient B – Phase

Colour gradients with a positive effect, Patient B – Phase 2

A. Identical positive preference reaction:

- Savannah 2, Deciduous forest 6, Mountains 7, Coast 9.1/9.2/9.3, Field 11.1/11.3

B. Identical negative preference reaction:

- Desert 1, Rainforest 3, Tundra 4, Taiga 5, Deciduous forest 6.1/6.2, Mountains 7.1, Coast 9, Arctic 10, Field 11

C. Deviations in preference reaction:

- Steppe 8: Phase 1 positive → Phase 2 neutral/negative
- Field 11.2: Phase 1 positive → Phase 2 neutral

Overall, **18 out of 20 motifs (90% congruence)** showed identical valence responses between images and colour gradients, with only Steppe 8 and Field 11.2 shifting from positive to

neutral/averse.

5.3. Comparison between Patient A and Patient B

A. Common positive preference clusters (atmospheres and sequences)

- Coast 9.1, Coast 9.3
- Field 11.1, Field 11.3

B. Common negative/neutral preference clusters (atmospheres and trajectories)

Identical unresponsive/neutral (A) - negative (B):

- Savannah 2, Rainforest 3, Tundra 4, Taiga 5, Deciduous forest 6.1, Mountains 7.1, Steppe 8, Arctic 10, Field 11

C. Divergences

- Desert 1: A positive → B negative/aversive
- Deciduous forest 6: A neutral → B positive
- Mountains 7: A neutral → B positive
- Coast 9.2: A no reaction → B positive
- Field 11.2: A positive → B neutral
- Deciduous forest 6.2: A very averse → B negative
- Coast 9: A averse → B negative

5.3.1. Preference associations

Positive preferences (both patients):

- Coastlines + fields associated with openness, brightness, warm colours, horizon line
- Long viewing duration, relaxation, body leaning forward, joy

Negative preferences (both patients):

- Rainforest 3, Tundra 4, Taiga 5, Arctic 10, Mountains 7.1 associated with darkness, confinement, cold, menace
- Short viewing time, turning away, tension

5.3.2. Varying signal strength

Patient A: few but stable positive reactions with generally low expressiveness.

Patient B: high reaction density with clear positive/negative affect markers and variation effects.

6. Results

Both patients showed:

- stable preference clusters
- high reproducibility
- positive reactions to open, warm colour atmospheres (fields, coastlines)
- negative reactions to dense, visually complex, dark environments (Rainforest 3, Tundra 4, Taiga 5, Arctic 10, Mountains 7.1)

The high degree of agreement between image and colour gradient reactions suggests that the colour **atmosphere represents a primary influencing factor**.

7. Discussion

7.1. Classification within the state of the art

The present results can be classified within several established fields of research, but extend these by a central aspect: the observation that colour atmospheres can trigger comparable emotional and behavioural reactions even independently of representational image content.

1. Environmental psychology and evidence-based architecture

Studies show that visual environmental factors . in particular references to nature, light and colour design . have measurable effects on stress, aggression and well-being (Ulrich et al., 2018; Hellemans et al., 2020). The present findings further refine this perspective by showing that comparable reactions occur both to representational depictions of nature and

to their abstracted colour atmospheres. This suggests that it is not primarily the representational nature (e.g.

.nature motif.), but rather the underlying colour atmosphere, constitutes a central component of the effect.

2. Colour psychology and perception research

The Colour-in-Context theory (Elliot & Maier, 2012) describes colour-dependent effects as context-sensitive. The results of this study extend this approach by showing that, under conditions of severely limited cognitive processing, abstract colour atmospheres can trigger comparable affective-physical responses to those elicited by representational images, provided that the underlying colour and lighting mood is preserved.

3. Embodied cognition and affective neuroscience

In line with somatic marker theory (Damasio, 1994; 1999), sensory stimuli can activate stored emotional experiences. The observed immediate physical-affective reactions to colour atmospheres can be interpreted as embodied response patterns that are activated even without linguistic mediation, thereby providing direct access to emotional preferences.

4. Sensory processing in autism and schizophrenia

Research on sensory hypersensitivity shows that visual complexity, stimulus density and contrast ratios are decisive influencing factors (Robertson & Baron-Cohen, 2017; Butler et al., 2008). The present results confirm these findings and further show that, in particular, open, visually less dense and atmospherically coherent colour spaces are associated with

approach and relaxation, whilst dense and visually complex atmospheres tend to correlate with avoidance and tension.

It is particularly noteworthy that these differentiated response patterns were observed in patients who had previously been virtually unreachable through attempts at verbal communication. The results therefore suggest that colour atmospheres can be understood as a form of pre-verbal communication through which emotional preferences and behavioural dispositions can be indirectly inferred.

This suggests that the atmospheric qualities of visual environmental stimuli may represent a fundamental level of perception that remains effective even when cognitive and linguistic processing is impaired.

8. Theoretical implication: Primacy of atmosphere

The central theoretical implication of this study lies in a shift in focus from representational content towards atmosphere as an effective level of visual perception.

The results show that colour atmospheres . understood as the integrative effect of hue, brightness, saturation and spatial openness . can trigger comparable emotional and behavioural responses even independently of representational image content. This suggests that, under certain

conditions, the atmospheric qualities of visual stimuli constitute an independent and possibly primary level of influence.

This does not, however, mean that representational elements are meaningless. Rather, it suggests that they may recede into the background, particularly when cognitive and linguistic processing is limited, whilst the atmospheric qualities of colour remain effective.

This perspective follows on from:

- atmospheric theories of perception (Böhme, 1995),
 - Gestalt psychological approaches (Koffka, 1935),
 - as well as more recent models of predictive processing (Clark, 2013),
- and expands upon them with an empirically supported perspective on the role of colour atmospheres as an independent variable.

9. Methodological reflection

The combination of concrete images of nature and the abstracted colour atmospheres derived from them allows for a rare differentiation between colour effects and contextual effects. The high degree of congruence in the observed reactions represents a methodologically significant finding, as it indicates that colour atmospheres can be investigated as an independent variable and their effects can, at least to some extent, be considered separately from representational content.

At the same time, it must be borne in mind that the study was deliberately conducted under the real-world conditions of a forensic psychiatric facility. The limited standardisation of key variables and the absence of a formal coding scheme restrict comparability in the strict methodological sense, but in an exploratory context they allow for an open and phenomenologically grounded recording of behavioural reactions.

The fact that the observed effects occurred consistently and reproducibly under these conditions can also be interpreted as an indication of the robustness of the underlying mechanisms of action.

10. Implications for design and practice

The findings of this study allow for specific conclusions regarding the design of therapeutic

environments, particularly in highly sensitive clinical contexts such as forensic psychiatry.

The consistent behavioural responses observed indicate that colour atmospheres can be specifically employed for emotional regulation. Open, bright and warm colour atmospheres were associated with approach, relaxation and longer dwell times, whilst dense, dark and visually complex atmospheres correlated with avoidance, tension and reduced interaction.

This suggests that the design of patient rooms and therapeutic spaces should not be conceived primarily in functional or symbolic terms, but rather with a specific focus on atmosphere. The aim is to create environments that:

- promote emotional stabilisation,
- reduce sensory overload,
- mitigate aggressive behaviour,
- and support willingness to participate in therapeutic interventions.

Particularly for patients with limited communication skills, the spatial atmosphere can thus represent a pre-verbal form of therapeutic relationship-building.

Furthermore, the approach opens up a new avenue for identifying individual preferences: the systematic observation of behavioural responses to colour atmospheres enables an empirically grounded approach to subjective needs without the need for verbal communication.

Beyond the clinical context, the findings suggest that colour atmospheres may also play a fundamental role in emotional experience in everyday life, architecture, design and art . regardless of any specific meanings attributed to them.

11. Limitations

This study is subject to several methodological limitations that must be taken into account when interpreting the results:

- very small sample size (N = 2),
- no inter-rater reliability testing,
- no standardised coding system,
- no video-based validation of the observations.

At the same time, it should be emphasised that the study was deliberately conducted under the real-world conditions of a forensic psychiatric facility. Whilst the limited controllability represents a methodological limitation, it significantly increases the ecological validity of the findings.

The fact that the observed effects occurred clearly and reproducibly under these conditions speaks to the stability and practical relevance of the identified correlations.

12. Implications

Scientific

- Strengthening the role of colour atmospheres as an independent factor in visual perception
- Expanding non-verbal diagnostic approaches for groups of people with severe communication impairments
- Expanding opportunities to involve non-verbal individuals in participatory design processes

Clinical

- Foundation for the individualised, evidence-based design of patient rooms and therapeutic environments
- Potential to support emotional regulation, behavioural stabilisation and willingness to undergo therapy

Social

- Expanding our understanding of the perception and means of expression of non-verbal people
- Raising awareness of the importance of atmospheric environmental qualities in everyday life

13. Conclusion

The results of this study provide initial empirical evidence that colour atmospheres can influence emotional experience and behaviour as an independent variable . even independently of concrete image content.

At the same time, the study shows that visual colour atmospheres can provide access to patients. preferences and reaction patterns that cannot be reached through verbal means.

Should these findings be confirmed in further studies, this would have far-reaching consequences for perception research, evidence-based spatial design, and therapeutic and diagnostic approaches in clinical contexts.

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17. List of image sources (Appendix)

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18. Appendix

(A) Colour scheme / Phase 1

(B) Colour gradient / Phase 2

1. Desert – Source: Falkenpost via Pixabay

1. Desert – Edited using AI and Photoshop

2. Savannah – Source: ronbd via Pixabay

2. Savannah – Edited with AI and Photoshop

(A) Colour scheme / Phase 1

(B) Colour gradient / Phase 2

3. Rainforest – Source: Samuel Faber via Pixabay

3. Rainforest – AI-assisted and manually optimised

4. Tundra – Source: Pixabay

4. Tundra – AI-assisted and manually optimised

5. Taiga – Source: John De Leon via Pexels

5. Taiga – AI-assisted and manually optimised

(A) Colour scheme / Phase 1

(B) Colour gradient / Phase 2

6. Deciduous forest – Source: Rainer Eck via Pexels optimised

6. Deciduous forest – AI-assisted and manually optimised

6.1. Deciduous forest – Source: Terje Sollie via Pexels

6.1. Deciduous forest – AI-assisted and manually optimised

6.2. Deciduous forest – Source: Simone Vom Feld via Pixabay

6.2. Deciduous forest – AI-assisted and manually optimised

(A) Colour scheme / Phase 1

(B) Colour gradient / Phase 2

7. Mountains – Source: allPhoto Bangkok via Pexels

7. Mountains – AI-generated and manually optimised

7.1. Mountains - Source: onkelglocke via Pixabay

7.1. Mountains – AI-enhanced and manually optimised

8. Steppe & Prairie: Source: Pixabay

8. Steppe & Prairie – AI-assisted and manually optimised

(A) Colour scheme / Phase 1

(B) Colour gradient / Phase 2

9. Coast – Source: diego_torres via Pixabay

9. Coast – AI-assisted and manually optimised

9.1. Coast - Source: SKY-TOM via Pixabay

9.1. Coastline – AI-assisted and manually optimised

9.2. Coast – Source: Pixabay

9.2. Coast – AI-assisted and manually optimised

(A) Colour scheme / Phase 1

(B) Colour gradient / Phase 2

9.3. Coast – Source: 4lb via Pixabay

9.3. Coast – AI-assisted and manually optimised

10. Arctic & Antarctic – Source: Riccardo via Pexels

10. Arctic & Antarctic – AI-assisted and manually optimised

11. Field - JOGphotos via Unsplash

11. Field – AI-assisted and manually optimised

(A) Colour scheme / Phase 1

(B) Colour gradient / Phase 2

11.1. Field - Source: Stephan Widua via Unsplash

11.1. Field - AI-assisted and manually optimised

11.2. Field – Source: Caroline Sada via Unsplash

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11.3. Field – Source: Silvestri Matteo via Unsplash

11.3. Field – AI-assisted and manually optimised